

Does Spatial Resolution Matter? Exploring the Effect of Grid Cell Size on Vector-Borne Disease Transmission in an Agent-Based Model

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Abstract. Agent-based models (ABMs) help simulate vector-borne disease (VBD) transmission in explicit geographic space, yet the effect of spatial resolution on model outcomes is rarely examined systematically. This poster presents a stylised transmission model for dengue, transmitted by *Aedes albopictus*, that is implemented in GAMA. Using OpenMOLE, simulations are run across six grid cell sizes (10 m to non-spatial) with 100 Monte Carlo repetitions each. Outcomes are compared by total infections, peak timing, and spatial distribution of transmission events. Initial test runs suggest that model behaviour is sensitive to resolution choice; systematic analysis is ongoing to quantify the magnitude and robustness of these effects. The study contributes to the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP) discourse in spatial simulation by examining resolution as a methodological design choice in VBD-ABMs.

Submission Type. Model, Theory, Analysis

BoK Concepts. [GC1] Geocomputation and complex systems, [GC2] Spatial simulation modelling

Keywords. ABM, *Aedes albopictus*, POM, GAMA, OpenMOLE

1 Introduction

Vector-borne diseases (VBDs) such as dengue fever represent a growing burden on global public health, driven by the interplay of climatic, environmental, and anthropogenic factors (De Souza and Weaver, 2024; Carrington and Simmons, 2014). With the ongoing geographic expansion of competent vectors such as the tiger mosquito (*Aedes albopictus*), understanding

transmission mechanisms is essential for effective risk assessment and management.

Agent-based models (ABMs) are particularly well suited for studying VBD dynamics. They decompose the complex system into interacting components: mosquitoes, humans, and their (shared) environment. Additionally, they allow researchers to experiment with parameter settings and explore emergent patterns with such models, e.g. the dengue model by Maneerat and Daudé (2016). Further, ABMs address critical gaps identified in spatial epidemiology: In a systematic review of 482 studies, Morrison et al. (2024) found that mechanistic representations of spatial processes and virtual intervention testing are scarce. ABMs explicitly represent the mechanisms that produce spatial patterns and make transparent how spatial structure shapes transmission dynamics.

Scale is a fundamental aspect of spatial analysis and spatial simulations (O'Sullivan and Perry, 2013). Manson et al. (2020) identify space and scale as a core methodological challenge for spatial agent-based models, noting that spatial representation choices directly shape how agent interactions are modelled and which patterns can emerge. Wallentin (2017) reinforces this point from an ecological modelling perspective. She highlights that the geospatial context is key to understanding how individual-based processes manifest in macro-level patterns and argues for a more deliberate integration of spatial explicitness and scale considerations into simulation design. While the sensitivity of results to the aggregation level, i.e. the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (Openshaw, 1984), is well established in statistical epidemiology and authors like Bomblies (2014) showed how high-resolution modelling matters for vector-borne disease simulations, the specific effect of systematically

varying grid cell size on simulated transmission dynamics in VBD agent-based models has received little attention. VBD systems have a strong spatial heterogeneity in vector density, host distribution, and environmental factors, making transmission processes highly localised and non-linear. Changing spatial resolution is therefore expected to modify contact structures, local transmission intensity, and outbreak dynamics. Wise et al. (2023) demonstrated in a COVID-19 ABM that spatial models behave fundamentally differently from non-spatial ones. VBD systems introduce additional complexity: Transmission requires interaction between two agent types operating at vastly different spatial scales. While humans may travel several kilometres per day, mosquito movement is typically limited to approximately 100 metres. This scale mismatch means that grid cell size may disproportionately affect how vector-host encounters are represented, something entirely absent in single-host models.

In this work, we hypothesise that spatial resolution systematically influences simulated epidemic dynamics. Coarser resolutions are expected to artificially inflate contact rates by collapsing spatially separated agents into shared cells, while finer resolutions may fragment transmission chains. By varying resolution along a continuum from non-spatial (single cell) to fine-grained (10 m), this proof-of-concept study aims to quantify these effects and establish whether resolution constitutes a methodologically significant parameter requiring explicit justification in VBD models.

2 Methodology

2.1 Model Description and Workflow

We developed a stylised mechanistic model of dengue transmission via tiger mosquitoes implemented with the GAMA platform (Taillandier et al., 2019). While transmission parameters (e.g., transmission rate, time to recover) are informed by dengue literature, the model is deliberately not calibrated to empirical outbreak data to isolate the effect of spatial resolution from location-specific confounders. The model itself follows the ODD protocol (Grimm et al., 2020) and builds on a model developed in a master thesis by Wöhs (2025).

The model environment is defined using administrative boundaries and a greenness-index raster derived from the Sentinel-2-based Sen2Cube platform (Sudmanns et al., 2021), serving as a proxy for mosquito habitat and, thus, risk area definition. The area of interest is taken from the base model by Wöhs (2025), a community in Salzburg, Austria, covering approximately 10 km². Human agents (n=3,000, which is approximately the number of inhabitants of the aoi) are initialised with one infected

individual; mosquito agents remain latent in risk area cells and are activated upon human-cell contact. Temporal resolution is set to 8-hour time steps over several weeks. Agents move via correlated random walk, and transmission follows probabilistic rules upon vector-host encounter.

Using the direct sampling algorithm of OpenMOLE (Reuillon et al., 2013), simulations are run across six resolution levels (risk cell sizes: 10 m, 50 m, 100 m, 500 m, 1000 m, and non-spatial) with 100 Monte Carlo repetitions each. The risk area aggregation uses a proportional approach, where each coarser cell is assigned the mean suitability of its sub-cells, representing the fraction of area containing suitable habitat rather than applying a binary classification that may overestimate risk at coarser scales. Following a pattern-oriented modelling approach (Grimm et al., 2005), outcomes are evaluated using three key metrics: total infected agents, time to infection peak, and spatial distribution of transmission events.

2.2 Data and Software Availability

The code and data files are published under a permissive CC-BY-SA 4.0 license and available at <https://github.com/kwoehs/spatialResolutioninVBDABMs-AGILE-poster-2026>.

3 Preliminary Results

Initial simulations suggest that model outcomes are sensitive to spatial resolution. Coarser grids tend to produce earlier and higher epidemic peaks, likely due to aggregated biting rates, whereas finer grids yield more spatially heterogeneous dynamics, including localized outbreak clusters (“hot spots”). Preliminary test runs confirm that raster configuration influences key transmission variables; however, further systematic analysis is required to quantify the magnitude and robustness of these effects. Ongoing work focuses on refining these comparisons and assessing their implications for model interpretation.

Declaration of Generative AI in Writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, Claude Pro was utilised for language editing, improving grammar, and sentence structure.

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